

NEW ANALYTICAL MODEL FOR REPAIRED CRACKED CONCRETE BEAM WITH COMPOSITE PATCH UNDER THREE POINTS BENDING MOMENT

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Abstract

The problem of increasing the longevity of damaged concrete structures is of major importance for economic reasons. The aim of this study is to analyze the mechanical behavior of a cracked concrete beam repaired with a composite patch. A finite element model was built to computerize the integral J around the crack localized along the beam thickness. The effects of different loading and repair parameters on the variation of the J-integral were analyzed. Based on these finite element calculations, we developed an analytical model for calculating the J-integral as a function of the various parameters. The results showed good agreement between the developed model and the finite element calculations.

Index Terms: Repaired Concrete Beam, Crack, Flexural Behavior, Composite Patch, J Integral, Finite Element, Adhesive.

1. INTRODUCTION

Techniques for repairing structures using composite materials involve bonding laminated composite plates made of carbon or worm fibers to thermosetting epoxy or polyester polymer matrices [1], [2], [3], [4].

This passive repair principle is an innovative alternative to the traditional solution using bonded outer metal plates, which allows [5-8] to increase the strength of degraded or damaged structures, or those subject to design or execution faults, in order to extend their

service life [9,10] and adapt the structure to changes in operating conditions or increase its load-bearing capacity.

Composite materials are used in this technique because of their high strength and lightweight properties. Bonding composite to concrete is simpler than with metal structures, which have higher weights and less significant stiffness. Repairing concrete structures with a composite patch induces a reduction in stresses in the repaired structure [11-13]. Some of these stresses are transferred from the concrete structure to the composite patch through the adhesive layer. This transfer takes place mainly by shear in the adhesive layer [14-15].

However, composite materials have a number of drawbacks, mainly due to their matrixes formed from thermosetting resins. These resins are highly sensitive to the external environment: sensitivity to ultraviolet rays, sensitivity to temperature and sensitivity to humidity [16]. These external factors lead to aging of the composite and consequent degradation of its mechanical properties over time [17].

In the repair technique, adhesives are used to bond the repair composite to the damaged concrete structure. Bonding offers several advantages over other types of assembly [18]. Adhesive bonding enables uniform stress transfer from the damaged structure to the composite patch [19]. However, being thermosetting resins, adhesives can also degrade over time, resulting in debond between the repaired structure and the composite patch. This debond likely to reduce the effectiveness of the repair [20].

The shear failure of a concrete beam is brittle and catastrophic. To remedy this, standard dimensioning methods call for the installation of transverse reinforcement such as stirrups. However, this type of reinforcement, in addition to being problematic for slabs, requires significant manpower and increases steel density, which can compromise concrete placement [20,21].

The technique of repairing cracked concrete structures with composite patches can be an effective means of restoring the rigidity of these structures and increasing their service life, provided that crack sizes prior to repair do not exceed critical thresholds [22]. In order to design repair patches for cracked concrete beams, the use of well-known fracture mechanics concepts such as the stress intensity factor or the J-integral is an effective means of assessing repair effectiveness. These concepts are little used in the literature for concrete structures.

In this study, the three-dimensional finite element method will be used to calculate the stress intensity factor (SIF) used to characterize a crack initiated in a concrete beam repaired with a carbon/epoxy patch. A parametric study of the effects of geometric and loading parameters on SIF variation will be carried out.

This parametric study will make it possible for the first time to develop an analytical model determining the stress intensity factor for a crack initiated in a concrete beam and repaired.

2. FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

A finite element analysis is carried out in this work to determine the J integral around a lateral crack initiated in a concrete beam subjected to three-point bending. This crack is repaired by bonding a composite patch to the cracked region in order to reduce stresses around the crack. This finite element analysis has enabled us to develop an analytical model giving the integral J as a function of the various repair parameters. This model will enable technicians working in the field of concrete structure maintenance to predict damage to concrete structures.

2.1 Geometrical model

Consider a concrete beam with dimensions: beam length $L=320$ mm, beam cross-section ($b=38.1$ mm, $D=12.7$ mm). The beam is simply supported at its ends and subjected to three-point bending by a concentrated load of amplitude F in the middle of the beam. An edge crack of length a is initiated in the middle of the beam, parallel to the applied load but in the opposite direction. To repair this crack, a unidirectional carbon/epoxy patch is bonded to the cracked area, the length of the patch is $L_r=160$ mm, its thickness is $t_r= 3$ mm and its width is equal to that of the concrete beam. The adhesive used to bond the composite patch to the concrete beam is Araldite 2012 with the thickness of $t_a= 0.5$ mm. The behavior of the different materials is considered to be linear elastic, and the elastic properties of the different materials are given in Table1. Fig. 1. shows the geometric model of the repaired beam with the boundary conditions.

Table 1: The Geometric and Materials Properties Table

Element	Dimension (mm)	E (Mpa)	ν	G (Mpa)
RC Beam	$L = 320$	$E_{11} = 31\ 800$	$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0,201$	$G_{12} = G_{13} = 13\ 240$
	$b = 38,1$	$E_{22} = E_{33} = 30\ 260$	$\nu_{23} = 0,19$	$G_{23} = 12\ 710$
	$D = 12,7$			
Adhesive layer	$L = 160$	$2\ 520$	$0,36$	930
	$b = 12,7$			
	$t_a = 0,5$			
Carbon fibre composite	$L = 160$	$E_{11} = 74\ 800$	$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0,37$	$G_{12} = G_{13} = 16\ 950$
	$D = 12,7$	$E_{22} = E_{33} = 37\ 800$	$\nu_{23} = 0,02$	$G_{23} = 18\ 530$
	$t_r = 3$			

Fig 1: The reinforced concrete beam

2.2 Mesh model

The Abaqus finite element code was used to develop the finite element model of the geometric model shown in Fig. 1. The model consists of three superimposed layers, respectively characterizing the cracked concrete beam, the adhesive layer and the composite patch. The beam, adhesive and composite are meshed separately using 8-node brick elements with exactly the same mesh on the contact surfaces. The mesh was further refined to an element size of 0.01 mm using twenty such fine elements around the crack front. Fig. 2 shows a typical mesh model of the repaired concrete beam.

A convergence calculation was performed to ensure the accuracy of the calculation and optimize the mesh, we used in this analysis a total number of element of 10,123 with 9,056 elements in the concrete beam, 212 elements for the carbon/epoxy patch and 212 elements for the adhesive. We used the domain-integral approach [22] to calculate the J integral at the curved crack front in three dimensions. A local value of the J integral at each point of the crack front under a static loading condition is given by (1):

$$J(s) = \lim_{\Gamma \rightarrow 0} \int_{\Gamma} \left[W n_1 - \sigma_{ij} \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_1} n_j \right] d\Gamma \quad (1)$$

Where W is the density of the energy of deformation, σ_{ij} is the stress component, u_i is the displacement component, Γ is a small contour of integration and X_i is the local Cartesian coordinate system at the location s , the mode I J integral is related to the stress intensity factor (K) by (2), E and ν are respectively the Young modulus and the Poisson ratio of the concrete.

$$J = \frac{K^2}{E'} \quad (2)$$

$E' = E$ for plane stress conditions

$E' = E / (1 - \nu^2)$ for plane strain conditions

Fig 2: The mesh of repaired concrete beam

Fig 3: The Von Mises stress of repaired concrete beam

3. FINITE ELEMENT RESULTS

The Convergence tests stabilized the calculations and ensured their accuracy. Fig.3 shows the equivalent stress distribution (Von Mises) in the concrete beam repaired with the composite patch, as well as the deformation after application of the load, we note that

some of the stresses are transferred to the composite patch through the adhesive layer. This transfer relaxes the stresses around the cracked region and reduces the speed of the crack propagation, thereby reducing the risk of sudden beam failure. We have calculated the J-integral along the crack front and presented it in the figures below. The variation of the maximum value of this integral is presented as a function of different parameters. This maximum value will enable us to assess the effectiveness of the carbon/epoxy patch in repairing the cracked beam.

3.1 Comparison between repaired and unrepaired beam

In order to assess the effect of patch bonding on the fracture behavior of the concrete beam, we have presented in Fig. 4 the variation of the maximum value of the J integral as a function of crack length (a) for repaired and non-repaired beams. There is a significant difference in J integral values between the repaired and non-repaired cases of the concrete beam. While the value of this integral far exceeds the value of 26 MPa.mm for an unrepaired beam, it remains below 22 MPa.mm for a repaired beam, whatever the value of the crack length. This reduction in J-integral will certainly halt crack propagation, resulting in a longer service life for the concrete beam. The repair technique, which is based on the transfer of load from the damaged structure to the composite patch through the adhesive layer, reduces stresses in the repaired structure, which in turn reduces the energy required to propagate the crack.

Fig 4: Graph of $J=f(a)$ of repaired and non-repaired beams

3.2 Effect of the applied load on the repair efficiency

The applied load causes the crack lips to spread apart, resulting in a high propagation speed of the crack. This speed will depend on the amplitude of the applied load. The effect of the applied load on the effectiveness of the repair is therefore very important and requires in-depth analysis.

Fig. 5 shows the variation in integral J as a function of applied load for different crack lengths repaired by the carbon/epoxy patch. It can be seen from this figure that the effect of the applied load on the value of the integral J depends on the size of the crack. For a crack of 5 mm in length ($a/D= 0.39$), the value of the integral J remains practically constant when the applied load varies from 2 to 3 kN. This behavior can be explained by the fact that when the crack size remains sufficiently smaller than half the beam thickness (D), the opening of the crack lips is not sensitive, allowing the composite patch to reduce the risk of crack propagation.

For crack lengths of 6 and 7 mm, i.e. $a/D= 0.47$ and 0.55 , there is a noticeable increase in the integral J, particularly at high applied loads. When the applied load (for these cases) is weak the value of the integral J doesn't vary much compared to the case of $a=5\text{mm}$, giving the same repair efficiency. When the value of the applied load exceeds 10 kN, the values of the integral J increase quite significantly for both crack sizes ($a=6\text{ mm}$ and $a=7\text{ mm}$), the value of the integral J for both crack lengths being of the order of 30MPa.mm for an applied load of 5 kN. It can therefore be stated that when the crack size approaches or slightly exceeds half the beam thickness, the effectiveness of the repair remains acceptable for low applied loads.

For a crack length of 8 mm ($a/D= 0.63$), it can be seen from fig. 5 that the value of the integral J increases quite significantly with increasing applied load. The value of this integral is 70 MPa.mm for an applied load of 5 kN, which is two times the value recorded for $a=6\text{ mm}$ and $a=7\text{ mm}$. We can therefore deduce that the increase in applied load will cancel out the effectiveness of the repair if the crack length is much greater than half the beam thickness. It is therefore imperative to repair the cracked beam when the crack length does not exceed 40% of the beam thickness.

Fig 5: Graph of $J=f(\text{load})$ of repaired beams

3.3 Effect of the patch thickness on the repair efficiency

The quantity of composite to be bonded as a patch to the cracked beam represents an important parameter in the effectiveness of the repair and its cost. This quantity can be evaluated by the number of plies of composite that will be bonded to the beam, but since the carbon/epoxy plies are unidirectional, the quantity of composite can be represented by the thickness of the composite patch. Fig. 6 shows the variation of the J integral for the repaired crack as a function of crack length for different thicknesses (t_r) of the composite patch, the applied load was 5 kN. The figure shows that increasing patch thickness reduces the J integral, thus improving repair efficiency. This is true whatever the crack length. This behavior can be explained by the fact that increasing patch thickness will allow higher stress transfer to the patch, resulting in lower J-integral values. However, increasing the patch thickness indefinitely will increase the cost of the repair and encumber the repaired structure. It is therefore imperative to optimize this thickness, a task which will be carried out in future work.

Fig 6: Graph of $J=f(a)$ for different t_r of repaired beam's patch

3.4 Effect of the adhesive thickness on the repair efficiency

The quality of the bond between the concrete beam and the composite patch will have an important effect on the performance of the repair, and this can be assessed primarily by the mechanical properties of the adhesive and its thickness. If the adhesive selected is Araldite 2012, whose mechanical properties are well known, we thought it would be useful to vary the thickness of this adhesive and analyze its effect on the integral J around the repaired crack.

Fig. 7 shows the variation in J-integral as a function of crack length for different adhesive thicknesses. From the latter figure, it can be seen that the effect of adhesive thickness is

practically negligible when the crack length is less than 7 mm (a/D ratio less than 0.55), beyond this crack size value, the effect of adhesive thickness becomes more noticeable, and it can be seen that increasing adhesive thickness also leads to an increase in J integral, and consequently a reduction in repair performance. We can therefore conclude that great care must be taken when distributing the adhesive between the two bonds, to avoid an excessively thick layer resulting in high J -integral. In addition, the adhesive thickness must be uniform along the entire contact surface.

Fig 7: Graph of $J=f(a)$ for different t_a of repaired beam's adhesive

4. ANALYTICAL MODEL OF THE J INTEGRAL FOR REPAIRED CRACK

The results presented in the previous paragraphs show that the parameters influencing the variation of the integral J for a repaired crack are multiple: crack length, applied loading, patch thickness, adhesive thickness and the mechanical properties of the various materials. This prompted us to develop a new mathematical model for calculating this integral as a function of the various parameters. This model will enable us to estimate the rate of damage to the structure due to the presence of the crack, and to predict the effectiveness of the repair over time (during crack propagation). The model is written as follows in (3).

$$K = \sigma \sqrt{\pi a} f \quad (3)$$

The J -integral for mode I (J) can be expressed as written above in equation (2)

Where: σ is the applied stress, a is a crack length

f is shape factor, this shape can be written as in (4).

$$f = 22,08341 \left(\frac{a}{D}\right)^3 - 30,63188 \left(\frac{a}{D}\right)^2 + 14,27241 \left(\frac{a}{D}\right) - 1,49308 \quad (4)$$

D is the beam thickness

for unrepaired crack, the mode I stress intensity factor (SIF) is K .

In Fig.8 the values of J integral calculated can be drawn from the presented model (for unrepaired beam) are compared with those calculated by FE analysis for different crack length. We can see that the difference is very weak which allows us to validate our model for an unrepaired crack.

Fig 8: FEM results compared with analytical solution of un-repaired plate

For repaired crack the same type of equation was established but if the factor f is a shape factor in the case of an unrepaired crack, i.e. it depends only on the geometric parameters (a and D), in the case of a repaired crack this factor can be written in (5), (6) and (7) as:

$$f = \chi \xi \quad (5)$$

$$\xi = 16813,45936 \left(\frac{a}{D}\right)^3 - 24898,62579 \left(\frac{a}{D}\right)^2 + 12167,41182 \left(\frac{a}{D}\right) - 1853,32138 \quad (6)$$

$$\chi = \left(\frac{E_a}{E_c}\right) \left(\frac{t_a}{t_c}\right) \quad (7)$$

Fig.9 presents a comparison between the values of the J integral of the analytical model and those calculated by finite elements for a repaired crack. There is also perfect agreement between the two calculations, with the difference not exceeding 1%, which means that our model is valid and can be used in practice to analyze the effectiveness of crack repair in a concrete beam repaired with a composite patch when the structure is subjected to bending moment.

Fig 9: FEM results compared with analytical solution of repaired plate

5. CONCLUSION

The results found in this study show that the effectiveness of repairing concrete structures with a composite patch depends essentially on the applied load and the mechanical and geometrical properties of the composite and the adhesive. The reduction in J integral by the repair patch is essentially due to stress transfer between the cracked beam and the composite patch through the adhesive layer. It has been shown that it is preferable to repair a concrete beam only if the crack length does not exceed 40% of the beam thickness. The analytical model developed in this study showed very good agreement with finite element calculations. We look forward to developing further models for different concrete structures.

NOMENCLATURE

a	crack length
b	width of concrete beam
D	depth of concrete beam
f	shape factor
L	length of beam
tr	thickness of repair
ta	thickness of adhesive
E11	Young modulus longitudinal
E22	Young modulus transversal
E33	Young modulus transversal
ν_{12}	Poisson ratio
ν_{13}	

u_{23}
 G_{12} Coulomb modulus
 G_{13}
 G_{23}
 W density of the energy of deformation
 σ_{ij} stress component
 u_i displacement component
 Γ small contour of integration
 X_i local Cartesian coordinate system at the location s
 I the mode
 J integral is related to the stress intensity factor K
 X
 ξ

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